

Enhancing European Interoperability Frameworks to Leverage Mobile Cross-Border Services in Europe

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ABSTRACT

In times where personal contacts must be reduced and in-person meetings and appointments have become difficult, electronic services are continuously gaining relevance. This especially applies to the public-sector domain, where e-government services have become a main pillar for the interaction between citizens and public administrations. In the European Union (EU), such service must not only be provided on national level but must be made accessible to all EU citizens, in order to satisfy the needs of a converging European society. The EU and its legal bodies support the provision of pan-European e-government services by means of various legal and technical frameworks. Two relevant frameworks in this context are the Single Digital Gateway Regulation, which facilitates cross-border retrieval of user data, and the eIDAS Regulation, which enables authentication of users across borders by federating the EU Member States' national identity management systems. While each framework has already successfully proven its potential individually, challenges arise when both frameworks are combined and jointly used by e-government services. This effect is even aggravated, if these e-government services do not follow a classical browser-based paradigm, but instead make use of and rely on mobile technologies. The Horizon 2020 project mGov4EU tackles these challenges. It develops technical solutions to help e-government

services employ the full potential of the SDG and the eIDAS Regulation. Thereby, it especially focuses on mobile, i.e., app-based services. Technical solutions developed by mGov4EU will be evaluated by means of several mobile pilot applications. This paper identifies and describes the challenges addressed by mGov4EU and introduces mGov4EU's solutions to overcome them. This way, this paper proposes a strategy to leverage the full potential of SDG and eIDAS also in mobile application scenarios, and hence paves the way for future successful mobile cross-border services.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Security and privacy** → **Domain-specific security and privacy architectures**; • **Information systems** → *Specialized information retrieval*.

KEYWORDS

eGov, SDGR, eIDAS, eSignature, Digital Wallet, Access Control, OAuth2.0, iVoting

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1 INTRODUCTION

The EU Regulation on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market (“eIDAS Regulation”) [2] provides the legal basis for federating national electronic-identity management systems (“eID systems”) from EU

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Figure 1: eGov general cross-border usecase targeted by mGov4EU project

member states (MS) and for using electronic signatures and seals across the EU.

The technical interoperability system that has been developed on that legal basis enables citizens of an EU MS to authenticate with their personal national eID to authenticate at governmental bodies and service providers applications from other EU MS (see Fig. 1).

The Single Digital Gateway Regulation (SDGR) [33] aims at “facilitating online access to the information, administrative procedures and assistance services that citizens and businesses need” in a cross-border context, in order to enable the citizens “to trade, establish themselves and expand their businesses in another Member State”. One of the procedures is the Evidence retrieval, where Evidence defines an official, governmental document.

With the Proposal for a European Digital Identity (EUid) [6] and Revision of the eIDAS Regulation, the European Commission aims to give users direct control of their identity data by means of digital wallets. While most technical details are yet to be defined, the foreseen revision of the eIDAS Regulation and the introduction of a European Digital Identity will cause a paradigm shift and will extend existing eID systems by wallet components that enable offline scenarios.

To enable third party agencies, coming from business and eGov, to make use of the Evidence and relieve the citizen from the burden of providing the data as a copy, supporting the EU data protection regulation (GDPR) [1] is necessary. Thus, citizens need to be empowered to manage the access to their data, in this case eGov Evidences, through user-friendly (mobile based) access control interfaces.

The mGov4EU project is focusing on leveraging these evolving technologies and initiatives for building a platform for online eGov services that citizens can access from a mobile device in a cross-border context due to moving to another Member State or having multiple citizenships, eIDs and residencies.

This article presents the system design of mGov4EU platform that brings together the domains of eID, SDG and eSignature. The building blocks associated with these domains are aligned with

the recently proposed regulation for the trusted and secure European e-ID [6] introducing the European Digital Wallet empowering both natural and legal persons to use cross-border digital identity solutions. The following sections are structured as following: Section 2 introduces the background, Section 3 presents the system requirements, Section 4 describes the system design based on the description of an overall architecture and domain specific building blocks and Section 5 depicts one of the project’s pilot usecases related to Internet voting. Section 6 analyzes the potential sustainability of the project results and Section 7 provides the conclusion and outlook towards the future work.

2 BACKGROUND

Over the last decade the EU has been initiating and investing in the development of the cross-border e-services within the EU through several policies, funding programmes and political communications. In 2015 one of the main initiatives related to enabling the cross-border digital public services was the adoption of the Digital Single Market (DSM). This Initiative aims to create an ecosystem in which citizens and businesses can access the online services irrespective of their place of residence [25].

The main regulations that the EU has adopted to enable DSM for cross-border e-services are eIDAS and Single Digital Gateway Regulation (SDGR) [33]. The eIDAS regulation aims to enable the mutual recognition of the nationally issued eID means, e-signatures and trust services across the EU, while SDG regulation aims to facilitate the online access to administrative procedures through a central point of access to public administration, thus fostering cross-border digital public services. The implementing act specifying more details of the SDGR conform system is planned to be released by the end of 2021. In this dynamic context, the requirements analysis against the background in terms of eID, cross-border data exchange, access control, eSignature and Digital Wallet play a major role in the design of the mGov4EU platform.

One of the initiatives that is currently running in parallel is GAIA-X, from the German Ministry of Economy and Climate Protection

(BMWK, formerly known as BMWi), with a suite of projects focusing on different areas of digital services, e.g. eGov and eHealth. The GAIA-X technical architecture [28] presents similarities regarding the concepts of Data Consumer and Data Provider, the resulting discover-ability of services as well as the transition to self-sovereignty through verifiable credentials. At the same time, the mGov4EU tackles a very specific domain of eGov and mobile identity that has to stay interoperable with the eIDAS/eIDAS 2.0 (proposed) regulation. From this constraint, a major difference emerges, as mGov4EU is a project targeting cross-border scenarios between two Member States and the GAIA-X is only on the side touching this point.

2.1 Identity Management

EU member states had started to roll out national eID systems long before the eIDAS regulation came into force. These national eID systems have enabled citizens to securely authenticate at service providers in online applications. Early implementations of national eID systems have typically relied on **smart-card technologies**. Citizens have been issued with personalized smart cards, which they could use for securely logging in to online services. Mainly for usability reasons, user acceptance of smart card based solutions remained low in most countries. In recent years, **mobile eID solutions** have hence emerged in various countries as alternative to smart card based approaches.

For many years, the use of national eID systems has been limited to the own country, preventing authentication at foreign service providers. For instance, a German citizen was unable to authenticate at an Austrian service provider using her German national eID. The eIDAS Regulation has tackled this issue by defining a legal and technical framework to achieve interoperability between the various national eID systems of the different EU member states. The current implementation of the eIDAS interoperability framework relies heavily on the identity-management protocol SAML2 [11] and implicitly assumes the use of web browsers on classical end-user devices like desktop computers or laptops. This raises challenges when the technical interoperability framework needs to be used in mobile-only scenarios, where mobile end-user devices such as smartphones are involved, mobile apps are used instead of web browsers, and Open-ID Connect [31] replaces SAML2 as the preferred identity-management protocol, due to its easier applicability on mobile environments. The solution presented in this paper addresses this issue by enhancing the current technical eIDAS interoperability system such that it can support mobile-only scenarios as well.

In offline scenarios, identity information is not fetched from a central identity provider but exchanged directly between the user and the requesting service provider using a user-controlled wallet, which stores required attributes. By excluding the central identity provider from the authentication process, the user's privacy is enhanced, as the identity provider cannot learn at which service providers the user has authenticated.

2.2 Single Digital Gateway

On the technical level, the Single Digital Gateway Regulation of EU wide cross-border digital public services has its roots on the

eDelivery building-block [12] and the Once-Only Principle (OOP) [15] stemming from the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) funding programme. Unfortunately the understanding of the Once Only Principle varies. In some countries, for instance in Estonia, it means that all data needs to be stored in only one database, while in France, the term is more general and means that citizens and businesses need to provide personal data only once [26]. The main goal EU wide agreed consists in reducing administrative burdens on citizens and businesses.

The eDelivery framework includes specifications based on OASIS standards like the AS4 Profile message protocol for secure and payload-agnostic exchange of data and the Service Metadata Protocol (SMP) [3] for dynamically discover the capabilities of the nodes, that can be used for finding the appropriate server storing a specific document type.

The eDelivery architecture is based on a four-corner model, as can be seen in Fig. 2. This means that the Evidences (eGov documents) pass through four layers - the backend of the sender (C1), the senders' Access Point (C2), the receiver Access Point (C3) and the backend of the receiver (C4). The communication between these layers is enabled by the AS4 messaging protocol. The Access Points are the nodes that enable the technical interoperability between the heterogeneous IT systems in the EU.

With the Single Digital Gateway Regulation (SDGR) [33], the requirements for the EU cross-border communication system of digital public services for retrieving governmental documents were defined. The regulation clarifies the need for the system to support national nodes per Member State (MS) and EU central nodes that communicate in order to enable exchange of governmental documents between the Data Consumer and the Data Provider. The Data Consumer (DC) acting as the communication end hop on the Evidence requester (citizen or business) can use the SDG infrastructure for enabling retrieval of a citizen evidence from a Data Provider (DP) - the software component of the Evidence provider (the national authority).

2.3 Access Control

The User Managed Access (UMA) extension of the OAuth2.0 authorization framework [22] was defined by the Kantara initiative [4] and enables a requesting 3rd Party agent to use a permission token to request an OAuth 2.0 access token, e.g. JSON Web Tokens [24], for gaining access to a protected resource, in other words consent management. A very important aspect is that the process is asynchronous: the resource owner receives a notification of access request and only after the owner adds/modifies the access policies will then be an access token generated for the 3rd Party to access the data resource.

The access-right type defined by the data regulation GDPR [1] and considered by mGov4EU regarding a citizen Evidence is the right of reading, more exactly download. Several initiatives and projects have analysed the GDPR from the Semantic-Web point of view. We limit the list of the resulting descriptions to one of the most relevant: the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) [5] from W3C. Such a vocabulary is meant to be implemented on an authorization server in order to encode the access policies.

Figure 2: eDelivery 4 corner model [21]

2.4 eSignature

The eIDAS-Regulation [8] provides the legal framework for trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market. The regulation defines the legal effects of electronic signatures and seals, as well as requirements for advanced and qualified electronic signatures and seals. Art. 26 (b) of the eIDAS-Regulation [8] requires that an advanced electronic signature “is capable of identifying the signatory”. While this requirement is typically implemented using digital certificates based on the X.509 standard [23], the legal framework of the regulation is technology-agnostic and independent of the specific implementation and hence allows other technical implementations as well. An alternative approach for creating advanced electronic signatures, which is in line with pertinent European norms [18–20] and applied within mGov4EU, is to combine electronic identification with an advanced electronic seal in which the result of the identification is embedded as SAML2 assertion [11] for example. This approach is especially attractive for eID means which are not capable of creating digital signatures itself, like the German eID (“Personalausweis”) for example.

2.5 Digital Wallet

The term Digital Wallet has been used in different contexts over the past few decades. In the past, digital wallets have been mainly mentioned in the context of finance technology (Fintech) [9]. There, digital wallets were primarily associated with digital payments. Only recently, concepts behind digital wallets have also found their way to the identity-management domain.

With the latest advancement of the user-centric identity management model, including Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI), the term digital wallet has also been adopted from a digital identity perspective [29]. The already mentioned European Commission [6] proposal of a European Digital Identity (EUid) relies on the term Digital Identity Wallet to support citizens in maintaining control of their identity data when performing online interactions. In this context, Digital Wallets can be compared with physical wallets, which people use to store, manage, and use identity data in physical format (e.g., identity cards, student cards, etc.). In such a physical setting, the use of identity data (e.g., identity card) refers to the presentation of this data to a third party, who can assess the data holder’s identity based on the presented identity data (e.g., identity card). In a digital setting, the identity data is present in electronic form and stored within a digital wallet. Thus, using the identity data refers to electronically transmitting the identity data to a receiver [30].

3 SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

This section identifies relevant system requirements that must be considered during design and implementation of the proposed solution. The mGov4EU project mainly focuses on combining the SDG and the eIDAS frameworks. Accordingly, relevant requirements can be derived directly from the respective legal bases.

When analyzing the Single Digital Gateway Regulation (SDGR) [33], on the side of the evidence requester (the citizen or the third party organization), the information system:

- Must inform users on the procedure steps and necessary identification

- Must allow users to request evidences that could be submitted directly too
- Must rely on eIDAS eIDs
- Could rely on eID Attributes or evidence provided from the digital wallet
- Only one identification process may be required (federation), unless required Level of Assurance (LoA) changes
- Explicit request requires the name of the provider and the evidence type
- Evidence request elements are defined (logging and accountability)
- Portal of the evidence requester must provide a preview space

Regarding the interaction with the evidence providers (including intermediaries), the information system:

- Must support eDelivery Access Points
- Must be able to receive and pass on evidence or evidence references
- Could be able to provide evidence or evidence references to be stored to Digital Wallet

Relevant system requirements for the proposed solution's eID part can be derived directly from the eIDAS Regulation and its related legal provisions. These requirements can be summarized as follows:

- Users must be able to authenticate at foreign service providers using their respective national eID means.
- User authentication takes place in the user's home country, i.e. the user must be redirected through the eIDAS framework from the service provider located in a foreign country to the eID system in her home country.
- The cross-border authentication process must be widely transparent to the service provider, i.e., the process for the server provier should be the same irrespective whether authentication is done nationally or delegated to another country.
- The user must be able to select her home country during the authentication process.
- The system should also support to use of identity wallets for providing required identity attributes. This means that during authentication user identity data can also be fetched from a digital wallet instead of the eID system in the user's home country.

For supporting the European Digital Identity, in the course of being regulated by the European Commission [6], the digital wallet is required to store and manage eID attributes for identification and authentication purposes towards online services.

The mGov4EU project aims to provide solutions especially for mobile usage scenarios, in which users access e-government services via a mobile app instead of web browsers. Accordingly, the above-mentioned requirements can be amended by the additional requirement that the proposed solutions must be compatible with purely mobile usage scenarios. Furthermore, they need to integrate tightly into existing mobile infrastructures. For instance, the resulting solution must provide support for those platforms and protocols that are already established and broadly used in mobile scenarios.

4 SYSTEM DESIGN AND INNOVATIVE ASPECTS

This section shows how the presented solution, with the architecture depicted in Fig. 3, combines various building blocks from the related domains for enabling citizens mobile cross-border services in order to meet the system requirements defined in Section 3.

4.1 Overall Architecture

Some of the mGov4EU project's innovations are related to integrating SDGR and eIDAS related building blocks, supporting Single Sign On across EU Member States and introducing user-managed access control for downloading eGov evidences. Considering the SDGR, another innovation of mGov4EU is to use the citizen's digital wallet for storing downloaded eGov evidence in a predefined digital format and thus allow the citizen an user-controlled management over the usage towards online services.

The resulting software architecture of the mGov4EU project depicted in Fig. 3 has been developed following the C4 modelling approach [10]. Following the established terminology of the C4 modelling method, each relevant (in our case innovative) building block denotes an individual System and is marked in blue and the legacy (e.g. National eID System, SDG infrastructure) and general building blocks (e.g. Data Provider and Service Provider) are marked in grey. The overall architecture contains the following five systems related to: eSignature, eSignature Interoperability, SDG Interoperability, eID Interoperability and Digital Wallet.

The entry point for the user is the Service Provider System, which implements and provides to the user a specific service, e.g., by means of a web application or a mobile app. In most cases, the Service Provider System asks the user to authenticate before access to provided services is granted. The user hence is routed to a suitable identity provider that can assert the user's identity. This routing can be challenging especially in technically heterogeneous cross-border settings, where specifics of national identity providers are typically unknown to the Service Provider System. The required routing functionality is implemented and provided by the proposed solution's eID Interoperability System, which redirects the user to a suitable national eID System acting as identity provider and asserting the user's identity. Alternatively, the role of the identity provider can also be assumed by the proposed solution's Digital Wallet System, which can store the user's identity information and can provide this information to the Service Provider System. This can be especially relevant in mobile use cases and usage scenarios, which the proposed solution is mainly targeting.

The role of the eSignature Interoperability System is similar to the eID Interoperability System in the sense that it routes the user to an intended system. However, in the case of the eSignature Interoperability System the routing target is not an identity provider but a suitable eSignature System, which enables the user to create (qualified) electronic signatures when requested by the Service Provider System. Note that in most cases the eSignature System, which the user is routed to, requires identification and authentication of the user. This is carried out in the same manner as identification and authentication at a Service Provider as described above. Hence, in this context the eSignature Systems assumes the role of a Service Provider System. After successful user authentication (either via

Figure 3: mGov4EU System Landscape diagram.

a national eID system or a digital wallet), the eSignature System creates the requested electronic signature on behalf of the user and returns it to the requesting Service Provider System.

Finally, also the SDG Interoperability System can be utilized by the Service Provider System (i.e., a Data Consumer in SDG terminology), if cross-border retrieval of any SDGR-related evidence is needed. Thus, the SDG Interoperability System provides a feature to retrieve requested evidences through existing SDG Infrastructure from an Data Provider. Retrieved evidences can then be forwarded to the Service Provider System and optionally also be stored in the user’s Digital Wallet. If the SDG Interoperability System requires user identification and authentication, similar considerations apply as for the eSignature Interoperability System. The SDG Interoperability System assumes the role of a Service Provider System and employs necessary eID-related Systems to authenticate users or validate that the service request is part of a Single Sign-On session.

The subsequent subsections focus on the overall solution’s various Systems and explore their internals.

4.2 eID Interoperability System

The eID Interoperability System, depicted in Fig. 4, provides components that enable cross-border authentication processes based on national eID solutions in mobile-only scenarios. It relies on components of the eIDAS technical interoperability framework but enhances these components to make them mobile-enabled. Thereby, the System supports two basic cross-border authentication scenarios.

In both scenarios, a User from Country A aims to authenticate with his National eID at a Service Provider from Country B (which can also be the SDG Interoperability System or the eSignature System) using an eID issued by Country A.

- In the first scenario, the eID Interoperability System forwards the User from the Service Provider in Country B to the User’s National eID System in Country A, where the User is authenticated. The User’s identity data is obtained

Figure 4: eID interoperability system components and interfaces

from the respective eID System and transferred back to the Service Provider in Country B.

- In the second scenario, the eID System in Country A is not contacted, but required identity data is fetched from the Digital Wallet (i.e., through Digital Wallet System) and transmitted directly from that System to the Service Provider in Country B.

In general, the following variants on how eID attributes could be provided to the Digital Wallet and how later users could use those eID attributes from Digital Wallet for cross-border identification and authentication towards Relying Party (i.e., Service Provider) can be identified:

- Variant A: eID attributes of User from Country A are to Digital Wallet provisioned via National eID System from Service Provider Country B using eIDAS Interoperability Framework. [Provisioning-SP-Country]
- Variant B: eID attributes of User from Country A are to Digital Wallet provisioned directly from National eID System from User Country A, i.e., eIDAS Interoperability Framework is not utilized. [Provisioning-User-Country]

For both variants, it is assumed that the User already possesses a valid (notified) eID means that can be used to authenticate at foreign Service Provider based on the eIDAS Interoperability Framework.

As shown in Fig. 4, the proposed solution applies [*Provisioning-SP-Country*] to avoid potential identity matching issues in the cross-border context, which may appear if the User Country is not the same as Service Provider’s Country.

Identity matching becomes necessary, when the Service Provider Country receives eID attributes from another country via the eIDAS interoperability framework and needs to map these attributes to the user’s existing attributes already stored in the SP country. This can be challenging as the set of required and stored eID attributes typically differs between different countries. The eID attributes are provisioned to the User’s Digital Wallet through the newly introduced eID Provisioning Service, located in Service Provider Country and thus connected to Service Provider’s National eID System. The eID Provisioning Service is a web application via which the User initiates provisioning of eID attributes. If the User is not from the same country as the service provider, authentication is performed by using the eIDAS Interoperability Framework as described before. After the User is authenticated, eID attributes are forwarded to the eID provisioning service and a QR code is displayed to the User, which encodes an access token. The access token is collected using a mobile device camera and used to establish an authenticated channel to the eID Attribute Provisioning REST API. eID attributes can then be fetched into a digital wallet through this channel. Users can later use those eID attributes to identify and authenticate themselves towards Service Providers from which country the eID attributes were provisioned. Focusing on cross-border aspects, if Service Provider national eID System provides eID attributes after a user was identified and authenticated via the eIDAS Interoperability Framework, the eID attributes are already in the format that Service Providers in that Country expect. In contrast, if the User national eID System provides eID attributes after identification and authentication through the User national eID System, eID attributes in Digital Wallet are not in the format that Service Provider from the non-user Country could expect. In that case, identity-matching problems may occur since some presented eID attributes are likely not in the same format fitting for Service Provider Country.

4.3 Digital Wallet System

In the scope of Digital Wallet, the identity-related data is here named Credential. This naming was mainly inspired by the Verifiable Credential Data Model [7], a W3C recommendation for expressing verifiable information on the Web, and an essential requirement that all identity-related data stored in the Digital Wallet should be verifiable. Thus, the term Credential could be described as a placeholder for any identity-related data and, in our case, annotates eIDAS (i.e., eID attributes) and SDGR (i.e., SDG evidence) related data.

As depicted in Fig. 5, a Digital Wallet is a mobile application that empowers Users to manage their Credentials in a user-controlled manner. Therefore the user can view, delete, store, and present credentials using this application. At the same time, all transactions, including credentials in the scope of the Digital Wallet, should be transparent to the user, i.e., with every transaction that includes identity-related data from the Digital Wallet, a user should be notified. Moreover, the user must consent before any credential is

stored (i.e., provisioned) into a digital wallet or presented (i.e., used) outside the Digital Wallet.

Focusing on eID attributes, whose provisioning has been described above (see section 4.2), different variants on how eID attributes from a Digital Wallet in the cross-border setting could be provided towards Service Provider can be identified:

- Variant A: eID attributes are provided to the Service Provider via the existing eIDAS Interoperability Framework. [*Wallet-Auth-eIDAS*]
- Variant B: eID attributes are provided to the Service provider via a partially adopted eIDAS Interoperability Framework. [*Wallet-Auth-eIDAS-adopted*]
- Variant C: eID attributes are provided to the Service Provider directly, i.e., from a Digital Wallet to the Service Provider System. [*Walet-Auth-SP-direct*]

[*Wallet-Auth-eIDAS*] and [*Wallet-Auth-eIDAS-adopted*] foresee usage of the existing eIDAS Interoperability Framework. They could be relevant if the eID attributes have been provided to Digital Wallet as described in [*Provisioning-User-Country*] before. Cross-border identity matching is thus achieved via authentication towards Service Provider using eIDAS Interoperability Framework, i.e., eID attributes are in the expected format for Service Provider. However, direct authentication from the Digital wallet towards the Service Provider system is not possible, as this would bypass any component of the eIDAS Interoperability Framework, and thus, identity matching in a cross-border context cannot be achieved.

In contrast, the [*Wallet-Auth-SP-direct*] entirely drops the existing eIDAS Interoperability Framework when eID attributes from a digital wallet are used for authentication towards the Service Provider. But, [*Wallet-Auth-SP-direct*] is possible only if the eID attributes have been provided to the Digital Wallet by the Service Provider’s national eID System, i.e., cross-border identity matching has been already performed within the eID attributes provisioning process - i.e., [*Provisioning-SP-Country*] has been applied for eID attributes provisioning. We chose to follow [*Provisioning-SP-Country*] (for details, see Section 4.2) for eID attributes provisioning, [*Wallet-Auth-SP-direct*] on how eID attributes are used for identification and authentication is applied. With [*Wallet-Auth-SP-direct*], the Service Provider could request eID Attributes directly from the Digital Wallet, thus enabling User authentication without interaction between intermediaries, i.e., national eID Systems or eID Interoperability Framework. In the same manner, as described in the Service Provider case, the Users can, with the usage of the Digital Wallet, authenticate themselves to any other system (e.g., eSignature or SDG Interoperability System).

Concerning the SDGR layer’s relation towards the digital wallet, no system exists yet to the best of our knowledge, which combines two different concepts on how identity-related data should be managed. The mGov4EU Digital Wallet building block will enable that once the SDG evidence is obtained through the SDG Interoperability System, it could be stored via the SDG Infrastructure into the Digital Wallet. Moreover, the Digital Wallet also enables Service Providers to perform a lookup of stored SDG evidence against user approval. This feature prevents unnecessary evidence retrieval via SDG Infrastructure of an evidence stored in the Digital Wallet. This functionality increases the usability of the system and at the same

Figure 5: Digital Wallet System components and interfaces.

time it avoids overloading of the SDG infrastructure and of the Data Provider.

4.4 SDG Interoperability System

The main functionality of the SDG Domain is to enable a Data Consumer (the citizen owning the data or a third party organization) to retrieve an Evidence from the Data Provider with the Consent of the Evidence Owner (the citizen). The SDG nodes between the Evidence Requester and the Evidence Provider constitute the SDG infrastructure administered by MS national and EU authorities, e.g. the AS4 Access Points forwarding the AS4 messages, and the Data Provider Discovery Service (SMP Server).

The components and exposed interfaces of the SDG interoperability system are depicted in Fig. 6. Once an evidence is generated for an owner, the Data Provider will register the evidence at the Authorization Server. When a request to retrieve an evidence is received from the Service Provider App (e.g. the one from iVoting use case), the mobile SDG App, running on the Data Consumer

(DC) side, will first check the Authentication status and the authentication credentials provided from the Service Provider App. After this, the Data Provider matching the required evidence type is discovered using the SMP protocol. Before sending the request to retrieve the evidence, an authorization token will be retrieved from the Authorization Server using User Managed Access profile of OAuth2.0. When the token is received, it will be included in the "Retrieve evidence" request, which will reach the Data Provider (DP). The DP will check the validity of the token and reply with the evidence.

For supporting the case in which the evidence is retrieved by a 3rdParty and not by the evidence owner, the Consent Management functionality from the Authorization Server will match the access policies in order to check which access (if any) to grant. When there are no matching policies, a notification will be sent to the data owner registered device and the data owner can asynchronously edit the policies.

After receiving the evidence, the Data Consumer is presented with an evidence preview in order to decide the next steps regarding

Figure 6: SDG interoperability system components and interfaces

the further usage of the evidence, e.g. store it in the Digital Wallet System with an annotation of evidence type and Data Provider identifier or forward it to the initiating Service Provider App.

Regarding the possible variants of the SDG interoperability system, a notable variant comprises of adding a history of matched policies in order to allow the evidence owner to track the exchange log.

4.5 eSignature Interoperability System

The eSignature building block (cf. Fig. 7) aims at demonstrating cross-border interoperability with respect to electronic signature technology supporting a variety of different eID means with different degrees of mobile support ranging from completely mobile signing solutions (Austria) via contactless eID means supporting NFC (Germany) to derived credentials stemming from contact-based eID means (Estonia, Belgium). It consists of an eSignature App and an eSignature Frontend which allow the User to interact with the eSignature Interoperability System and the eSignature Client, which makes appropriate API calls at the eSignature Backend, which finally takes care about the creation of signatures and seals.

5 IVOTING USECASE

In Internet voting solutions, it is necessary to ensure the principle of data privacy for the voters as well as the integrity and secrecy of the votes. Violation of uncoercibility and secrecy-security prerequisites could lead to the loss of trust and consequent abandoning of the technology since the electorate would be vulnerable during the election procedure. In order to ensure these core principles are intact, when translating the iVoting use case for mGov4EU project piloting purposes, state of the art tools of encryption will be employed.

Additionally, it is also essential to ensure the authenticity of the voters and their eligibility in the election process, i.e., they are authorized to vote in a particular process. Otherwise, the election outcome could be manipulated by tallying votes from non-eligible voters, thus posing the election integrity at risk. The iVoting use case will make use of the eID and SDG building blocks to get cross-border mobile eIDAS authentication and evidence retrieval with user consent for obtaining voter authorizations (see Fig. 8).

The mGov4EU iVoting pilot will start in the year 2023 and will validate the architecture in a cross-border setting having the University of Tartu, Estonia, as one of the piloting sites. The goal is to

Figure 7: eSignature Interoperability System

build a pilot similar in requirements to an online European EU Parliament election, in which evidences (eID and/or citizen attributes obtained via SDG) will be used to demonstrate the right to vote and the fact that the citizen did not vote or did not request vote by post, and propose the resulting demonstrator to the regulating authorities.

In terms of the use case development, the first step is to provide a unique mapping between a person (e.g. a voter) and their identifiers, which could be obtained from various EU MSs. The second step is then to incorporate the mapping into a solution (e.g. a web-based application) that can be used by the platform for i-voting. As the issue was already identified in the context of the amendment of the eIDAS regulation it is expected that a general solution will be provided as part of the new eIDAS regulation and can be reused for the mGov4EU project. This architecture would provide additional safeguards for personal data privacy and ballot secrecy since it will be based on already tested and proven systems.

Complementary subtasks will be the gathering of voter authorizations, issued by one or more entities that will have the function to authorize voters to vote for a given election. These voter authorizations will be obtained by requesting the voter’s consent to access them using the SDG-Layer. Another possible, optional, subtask is the signature of the vote using the signature services provided by the project. Finally, the last aspect is that since the pilot has far-reaching goals, information about the electorate’s overall

perception of the interface and/or voting process would benefit the establishment of the final product.

6 SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS

Regarding the cross-border online services in EU, the third pillar of the Digital Single Market (DSM) [16] on overall growth of digital economy specifies the need for enabling interoperable cross-border e-services that should be included in the e-Government action plan. Thus, the e-Government Action Plan for 2016 – 2020 set up the goals and strategic objectives on enabling cross-border e-services and easing public sector interactions with citizens [17].

Furthermore, in the mid-term review of the DSM in 2017 it is stated that there is need for further progress on, inter alia, European public services which are result of the increased demand of businesses and citizens. The latest initiative by EC is the Digital Europe Programme for the period of 2021-2027 which aims to reinforce set up goals and impact of the Digital Single Market policy achievements ([32]).

Other initiatives that aim to enable (mobile) e-services across the EU is also the European Interoperability Framework (EIF) and European Interoperability Reference Architecture. These initiatives provide a framework and architecture for designing interoperable and digital-by-default e-services. From the legal perspective, several regulations have been adopted to ensure the cross-border e-services in the EU.

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